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School Administrators' Behaviors in the Professional Belonging of Teachers

Mehmet Özdođru¹

¹ Faculty of Education, Kütahya Dumlupınar University, Kütahya, Turkey

Correspondence: Mehmet Özdođru, Kütahya Dumlupınar University, Educational Administration, Kütahya, Turkey. Email: mehmetozdogru26@gmail.com

Abstract

In this study, it is aimed to examine the behavior of school administrators in the context of teachers' professional belonging. The research was designed in the phenomenology pattern in the qualitative research method. In the study, 25 teachers working in the province of Eskişehir formed the study group. A semi-structured interview form was used to examine the behavior of school administrators in the context of teachers' professional belonging. In the collection of data, face-to-face interviews were conducted with the participants, and the analysis of the data was carried out in accordance with the content analysis method. According to the findings, teachers' views on the behaviors of school administrators, which increase teachers' professional belonging, are gathered under four themes: administrative behaviors, effective communication, behaviors based on personality traits and behaviors towards meeting social needs. The behaviors of school administrators, which reduce the professional belonging of teachers, are grouped under three themes: managerial behaviors, negative communication and behaviors based on personality traits. When the research findings are evaluated in general; It is seen that the behaviors of school administrators have an important place in the professional belonging of teachers. The fact that the teaching profession is a profession that requires great dedication reveals the importance of the concept of professional belonging, which is one of the important factors affecting the organizational behavior of the individual.

Keywords: Professional Belonging, Teacher, School Administrator, School Principal, Belonging

1. Introduction

The success of education systems is measured by the effectiveness of the school. Effective schools have a strategic role in the formation of a strong education system (Akan, 2007). An effective school can be defined as a school where students' cognitive, affective, psychomotor, social and aesthetic developments are supported in the most appropriate way and an optimum learning environment is created (Özdemir, 2000).

One of the important factors affecting student success is the quality of the teacher. There are many studies on the effect of teacher quality on student achievement (Akbaba Altun, 2009; Bedi & Marshall, 1999; Darling-Hammond, 2000; Rivkin, Hanushek, & Kain, 2005). One of the resources that educational organizations most

need is qualified workforce. However, it is also important for employees to identify themselves with their profession and institutions, and to strive for the success of the institution, in addition to having certain qualifications. This situation necessitates the high level of professional belonging for the employees (Keskin and Pakdemirli, 2016, p.2585).

Occupational belonging refers to “the combination of all attitudes nurtured by various aspects of an individual's profession” (Erdoğan, 1996). The concept of professional belonging was first defined by Greenhaus in 1971. While Greenhaus (1971) defines professional belonging as “the gaining importance of the profession in the life of the individual”; Aranya, Pollock & Amernic (1981) defined it as “the relative power that an individual identifies with his occupation”.

Professional belonging is the main factor that increases and sustains the motivation and performance of employees in business life. From this point of view, it has gained importance in recent years for both the employee and the employer (Keskin and Pakdemirli, 2016, p.2585). One of the reasons that prompt the individual to work is the formation of a sense of belonging and identity in the individual (Aslan, 2001). The more an individual adopts the values and goals of the business organization and institution, or the more he or she feels belonging to the business organization and institution, the more willing he is to work for the benefit of that organization and institution (Ören et al., 2005, p.5; Sevinç & Şahin). , 2012, p.266).

Professional belonging is directly related to the professional life and quality of life of individuals and directly affects professional satisfaction (Özdevecioğlu & Aktaş, 2007). Belonging to the profession directly affects job performance (Lee et al., 2004). Professional belonging is extremely important in motivating an employee. The productivity of the employee can improve if he is motivated to work (Tella et al., 2007). Employees with high professional belonging are defined as those who have a strong belief in their profession, accept the aims of the profession, make an effort on behalf of their profession, and are willing to exist in the profession (Lord & DeZoort, 2001, p.6).

From the point of view of the teaching profession, it is very difficult for teachers to fully fulfill their duties and responsibilities without a high sense of belonging to their profession, considering the reasons such as the fact that teaching is a profession that requires great dedication, its responsibility is high, and it is in a very critical position in the rise of society. It is thought that a strong sense of belonging in the performance of the teaching profession will allow for an increase in performance as well as directly affect teachers' job satisfaction and professional satisfaction (Şenel, 2021).

School administrators' revealing their vision and goals within the scope of the school's mission with a sharing understanding and special behaviors with teachers and other employees is very effective in the formation and reinforcement of a sense of belonging in their subordinates and employees (Balci, 1993). The school principal needs to understand the thoughts, concerns, problems and expectations of the students and staff, who have many different characteristics such as cultural, ethnic origin, economic situation, and religion, and develop skills for the management of these differences (Balyer, 2012). It is difficult to say that the management behaviors that a school administrator will take without considering the characteristics of the teachers will increase the success of the school. The emotions experienced by the teachers as a result of the behaviors exhibited by the school administrators directly affect both his work performance in school life and his performance in daily life, and affect schools in an individual and organizational sense, positively or negatively (Argon, 2015).

School administrators have important duties to ensure that teachers are satisfied with the environment in which they work and to develop a sense of belonging. The most important of these is to try to integrate institutional and individual goals. The teacher's belief that he can achieve his individual goals improves his sense of belonging, enables him to identify with the institution and increases his efficiency (Karaköse, 2005). Behaviors of the school administrator can affect the teachers' performance in the educational process by having a positive or negative effect on the teachers and determine the degree of achievement of the school's goals. In a sense, this reflects the success level of the school (Yalçın, 2017).

In the literature, there are various studies on the professional belonging of teachers. Şenel (2021), who examined the perceptions of professional belonging of teachers in excess of norm in his study, concluded that the sense of professional belonging decreases as the year in which teachers are more than normative increases. Güler, Çıkrıkçı & Akçay (2020) found in their research that as teachers' perceptions of effective school increase, their perceptions of professional belonging also increase. Habegger (2007), on the other hand, concluded in his research that successful school principals increase the professional belonging of teachers through various activities. Aydınol & Üredi's (2020) study revealed that there is a significant difference between classroom teachers' sense of professional belonging and their professional satisfaction levels. When the studies on the subject are evaluated, it is possible to say that there are studies on the professional belonging of teachers. However, in the literature review, no research was found to determine the behaviors of school administrators, which are effective in the professional belonging of teachers. From this point of view, it is important to learn the behaviors of school administrators, which are effective in the professional belonging of teachers, in terms of the effectiveness of teachers.

Identifying the behaviors of school administrators, which are effective in teachers' professional belonging, and offering suggestions on this subject can contribute to increasing the effectiveness of teachers, thus improving student learning. In addition, it is thought that the results of the research are important in terms of determining the steps to be taken to increase teacher performance in reaching an effective school. With this research, it is expected to contribute to increasing the professional belonging of teachers by determining the behaviors of school administrators, which are effective in the professional belonging of teachers. In this direction, it is aimed to examine the behavior of school administrators in the context of teachers' professional belonging. In this direction, answers to the following questions were sought:

What are the views of school administrators who increase teachers' professional belonging?

What are the opinions of school administrators who reduce the professional belonging of teachers?

2. Method

The Method section describes in detail how the study was conducted, including conceptual and operational In this study, it is aimed to examine the behavior of school administrators in the context of teachers' professional belonging. The study was carried out according to the phenomenology pattern of the qualitative research method. In order to understand social reality, phenomenology focuses on the human experiences that this reality creates. In this context, experiences related to the phenomenon are questioned (Ersoy, 2016). In this context, the phenomenon of the study is the behavior of school administrators that increase and decrease the professional belonging of teachers. Considering that the participants of the study had experiences and observations about the behaviors of school administrators in the professional belonging of teachers, the study was carried out according to the phenomenology pattern.

2.1 Study Group

In the study, 25 teachers working in the province of Eskişehir formed the study group. While determining the participants, the maximum diversity sampling technique, which is a purposive sampling method, was used. Maximum diversity sampling; It is defined as the determination of similar and different situations related to the problem examined in the universe and conducting the study on these situations (Büyüköztürk, 2014). In the use of this technique, it is aimed to reach richer and more detailed data by providing the diversity of the participants. Personal variables such as seniority, gender and age were taken into account while determining the teacher in the study. In addition, care was taken to ensure that the schools where teachers work are at different levels (primary school, secondary school, high school), in different neighborhoods and in different socio-economic environments (lower-middle-upper). In this way, it is aimed to achieve diversity in terms of schools and therefore the problems experienced. Information about the study group is shown in Table 1:

Table 1:Information About Participants

Code	Gender	Type of school served	Branch	Seniority	Education level
T1	Female	Secondary School	Mathematics	11	Bachelor's Degree
T 2	Female	High School	Chemistry	15	MA Graduate
T 3	Male	Secondary School	Turkish	16	Bachelor's Degree
T 4	Female	Primary School	Primary school teacher	22	Bachelor's Degree
T 5	Female	Secondary School	English	16	Bachelor's Degree
T 6	Male	High School	Physics	25	Bachelor's Degree
T 7	Female	High School	Physical Education	17	Bachelor's Degree
T8	Female	Primary School	Primary school teacher	32	Bachelor's Degree
T9	Male	Secondary School	Social Studies	17	Bachelor's Degree
T10	Male	Secondary School	Physical Education	18	MA Graduate
T11	Male	Primary School	Primary school teacher	14	MA Graduate
T12	Female	High School	History	27	Bachelor's Degree
T13	Male	Primary School	Primary school teacher	24	Bachelor's Degree
T14	Female	Primary School	Primary school teacher	24	Bachelor's Degree
T15	Male	High School	Biology	21	Bachelor's Degree
T16	Male	Secondary School	Social Studies	12	Bachelor's Degree
T17	Female	High School	Geography	19	Bachelor's Degree
T18	Female	Primary School	English	14	MA Graduate
T19	Male	Secondary School	Turkish	17	Bachelor's Degree
T20	Female	Primary School	Primary school teacher	23	Bachelor's Degree
T21	Male	High School	Literature	24	Bachelor's Degree
T22	Male	High School	Mathematics	18	Bachelor's Degree
T23	Male	Primary School	Primary school teacher	19	MA Graduate
T24	Female	Secondary School	Science and Technology	17	Bachelor's Degree
T25	Female	Primary School	Primary school teacher	23	MA Graduate

2.2 Data collection tool

In the research, interviews were conducted with teachers in order to examine the behavior of school administrators in the context of teachers' professional belonging. In this direction, a semi-structured interview form was used in the research.

During the development of the data collection tool, a literature review was conducted, a conceptual framework was created on the subject, and opinions were received from two experts in the field of educational sciences. In line with the opinions of the experts, the number of questions in the form was reduced from three to two in order not to deviate from the purpose of the research. In order to make a preliminary test of the draft form, a pre-application was made with two teachers other than the participants of the study. After these applications, the form was given its final form. In the semi-structured interview form, there are eight questions in total, six for determining the demographic characteristics of teachers and two for the purpose of the research. The following questions were asked to the study group in order to examine the behavior of school administrators in the context of teachers' professional belonging.

What are your views on the behavior of school administrators that increase your belonging to the teaching profession?

What are your views on the behavior of school administrators that reduce your belonging to the teaching profession?

2.3 Data Collection

Interviews with the study group of the research were carried out by the researcher between February and March 2022. Interviews, in line with appointments from teachers. In order to enable teachers to express their feelings clearly and comfortably, it was held at the designated times in their own schools or wherever they wanted. Before starting the interviews, the participants were first informed about the purpose of the research with a consent form. Before starting the interviews, it was explained to the participants that the interview would take place in accordance with confidentiality and ethical principles, that the name of the person and institution would not be specified, and that the data obtained would be known only by the researcher, and approval of recording with a voice recorder was requested. However, three teachers did not allow audio recording, and the interviews with these teachers were recorded by taking notes by the researcher. The duration of the interviews with each participant was between 20-30 minutes. In the interviews, the participants were asked about the "opinions of the school administrators who increase the professional belonging of the teachers" and "the opinions of the school administrators who decrease the professional belonging of the teachers" and their demographic characteristics within the scope of the purpose of the study.

2.4 Analysis of Data

The data obtained as a result of the interviews were analyzed with the content analysis technique. In content analysis, the obtained data are analyzed in depth and concepts (codes) that can explain the data are revealed and these concepts are organized and interpreted under appropriate categories (themes) (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2018). Legislation and literature were used while creating themes. In the research, a total of 12 hours of interviews were conducted with 25 teachers. The audio recordings taken were deciphered and transcribed. In order to check the accuracy of the transcription process, the data obtained from the audio recordings and the data obtained from the interview form were compared. 87 pages of data were obtained from the interviews. The common points in the answers given by the participants to each question were determined and coded. The codes created by the researcher were presented to the opinion of two experts in educational sciences and qualitative research. The reliability of the research was determined by comparing the codes made by the experts with the codes made by the researcher. In this process, the formula of $\text{Reliability} = \left[\frac{\text{Agreement}}{\text{Agreement} + \text{Disagreement}} \right] \times 100$ (Miles & Huberman, 1994) was used. As a result of the comparison, the inter-coder reliability level was calculated as 89% and it was found to be consistent. In addition, direct quotations were made to reflect the views of the participants. In addition, in order to ensure participant confidentiality, the teachers participating in the research were abbreviated as Teacher 1 (T1), and the participants were given numbers.

2.5 Validity and Reliability Measures

Measures of validity and reliability in the study were taken into the framework of Lincoln & Guba's (1985) internal validity (credibility), external validity (transferability), internal reliability (consistency) and external reliability (confirmability) in qualitative studies. For this purpose, the following was done to ensure the validity and reliability of the research:

While preparing the interview questions to ensure internal validity, the literature was reviewed, and two experts from the field of educational sciences were consulted on whether the interview questions to be used would collect the necessary data. A pilot application was made to three teachers, other than the participants of the research, in order to make a preliminary trial of the prepared draft form. First of all, sufficient interaction was established with the participants for credibility. Before the interviews, it was explained that the interviews would be kept confidential and the purpose of the study was explained so that the teachers would feel comfortable. Permission was requested for the audio recording, and the interviews with the two teachers who did not give permission were recorded by taking notes. After the data obtained from the interviews were deciphered, they were sent to the participants (mail, whatsapp) and shared. The participants' confirmation was obtained by comparing the decipherers made by the researcher with what the participants wanted to express.

In order to ensure the external validity (transferability) of the research, each stage of the research was presented to the reader in detail and all processes were mentioned as clearly as possible. In addition, in order to increase external validity in the study, maximum diversity was tried to be provided in the study group. Particular attention was paid to including schools that accept students from different socio-economic environments, located in different districts and at different levels (primary and secondary school) into the study group.

In order to ensure the internal reliability (consistency) of the research, the consensus strategy between coders was used (Cresswell, 2013). The codes created by the researcher were presented to the opinion of two experts in educational sciences and qualitative research. The reliability of the research was determined by comparing the codes made by the experts with the codes made by the researcher. In addition, direct quotations were included to reflect the original views and thoughts of the participants.

Confirmation review method was used to ensure the external reliability (confirmability) of the research. The raw data obtained in the research and the results and comments made in line with these data were presented to the field expert for confirmation and the confirmation of the field expert was obtained. In addition, the notes taken during the research process, audio recordings, raw data collected, code structures used in the analysis phase were digitally archived by the researcher so that they can be accessed again when needed.

3. Findings

In this section, teachers' views on the behavior of school administrators in their professional belonging are given. The findings obtained from the interviews with the teachers are given below.

3.1 Behaviors of School Administrators Increasing Teachers' Professional Belonging

Teachers' views on the behavior of school administrators, which increase teachers' professional belonging, are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Behaviors of school administrators increasing teachers' professional belonging

Theme	Codes	
Managerial behavior	Fair and impartial behavior	Sharing authority
	Valuing and caring for the employee	Accountability and transparency
	Involvement in decisions	Problem solver
	Appreciating	Be consistent
	Stand by the employee	Democrat
	Trust the teacher	Being open to collaboration
	Improving physical conditions	Accommodating
	Reducing bureaucracy	Taking initiative
	Making things easy	Set an example
Empowering the teacher	Being informative and guiding	
Effective communication	Active listening	Inclusive speaking
	Persuasion	Using humor
	Providing feedback	Giving morale
Behaviors based on personality traits	Being honest and trustworthy	Showing understanding
	Show respect	Polite and courteous
	Empathy	Respecting differing opinions and views
	Being friendly	Control your anger
	Being tolerant and optimistic	Being open to criticism
Meeting social needs	Organizing social activities	Ensuring togetherness
	Meeting the need for rest	

According to Table 2, teachers' views on the behaviors of school administrators, which increase teachers' professional belonging, are gathered under four themes: administrative behaviors, effective communication, behaviors based on personality traits, and behaviors towards meeting social needs. School administrator behaviors that increase teachers' professional belonging under the theme of administrative behaviors; behaving fairly and impartially, valuing and caring for the employee, contributing to the decisions, appreciating being with the employee, trusting the teacher, improving the physical conditions, reducing bureaucracy, facilitating the work, empowering the teacher, sharing authority, accountability and transparency, problem solving, acting consistently, democrat It was expressed by the participating teachers as being open to cooperation, accommodating, taking initiative, setting an example, informative and guiding. School administrator behaviors that increase teachers' professional belonging under the theme of effective communication; Active listening, persuading, providing feedback, inclusive speaking, using humor and giving morale were expressed by the participating teachers. School administrator behaviors that increase teachers' professional belonging under the theme of behaviors originating from personality traits; being honest and reliable, showing respect, empathizing, being sincere, being tolerant and optimistic, showing understanding, being kind and gentle, respecting different thoughts and opinions, controlling anger and being open to criticism. School administrator behaviors that increase teachers' professional belonging under the theme of meeting social needs; It was expressed by the participating teachers as organizing social activities, meeting the need for rest and providing togetherness. Some of the opinions of the participating teachers on the subject are given below:

First of all, the school principal should manage his school fairly as an administrator. It should not discriminate among its employees and should treat them equally. Teachers should not always be task-oriented, and should be intertwined with teachers in normal times. It should be able to offer solutions to the problems faced by teachers. In this way, the teacher will not feel alone in his profession and will do his best. (T5).

I realized that our principal at the school I was first assigned to was loved by the teachers working in his school. As time passed, I got to know him better. Indeed, our principal was an administrator who was very sincere with the teachers, was interested in the problems of the teachers, and decided together with the teachers to work on the work to be done at the school. As teachers, we were working hard on the studies and activities to be done at the school. (T12).

First of all, the school administrator should see the school as a family and be integrative. He needs to establish an environment where everyone can help each other, as in the warmth of the family, and he should set an example in this. We teachers, who work in such an environment, do our duty properly. (T17).

The fact that our school administrators value teachers' opinions positively affects our commitment to our work. We feel valued and important. The feeling of doing more and being productive for my school increases. (T9).

I think it is very important for the school administrator to take care of himself when a teacher is sick or has a problem. Because it is a great source of morale and motivation for the teacher to receive attention and support from the manager in a difficult moment. As a result, the teacher will not feel alone at school, and a close bond will be formed between him and his profession. (T21).

From time to time, we are subjected to injustices while doing our duty. There are times when we have problems with parents. We are exposed to unfair accusations. In these moments, the attitude of our school principal is very important for us teachers. By standing next to his teacher, protecting the teacher against injustice and embracing his teacher also finds a response in the teacher. An emotional bond develops towards our school and our profession... (T23).

Teaching has become a difficult and stressful profession today. The problems of the students and the attitudes of the parents are quite abrasive when they are on duty. Most of the time, we get overwhelmed with things at school, and there are times when we feel overwhelmed. Social and sportive activities such as going out to dinner with fellow teachers and the school administration and organizing trips increase our belonging to our school and profession. (T 4).

Our school principal makes an extraordinary effort in the process of ensuring that the equipment we will use in the lessons is complete and the physical infrastructure of the school is ready for education. Most of the time he is trying to find sponsors to meet our needs. When we see these, we try to do our duty in the best way and try to support our manager.(T12).

3.2 Behaviors of School Administrators Reducing Professional Belonging of Teachers

Teachers' views on the behaviors of school administrators, which reduce the professional belonging of teachers, are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Behaviors of school administrators reducing professional belonging of teachers

Theme	Codes	
Administrative behaviors	Authoritarian and oppressive	Use of authority as a threat
	Overly prescriptive	Making decisions alone
	Discrimination	Not being a role model
	Biased	Not taking partial initiative
	Inability to come up with solutions	Ignore effort
	Referring	Affairs to someone else
Negative communication	Commanding	upbraiding
	Giving advice	Judgmental
	Blaming	"I" language
	Constantly criticizing	Shouting
Behaviors based on negative personality traits	Distrust	Avoidance of responsibility
	Insensitivity	Do not justify yourself
	Excessive skepticism	Interest-oriented
	Feeling superior	Not being open to criticism
	Inconsistency	

According to Table 3, teachers' views on the behaviors of school administrators, which reduce the professional belonging of teachers, are grouped under three themes: administrative behaviors, negative communication and behaviors arising from personality traits. School administrator behaviors that decrease the professional belonging of teachers under the theme of administrative behaviors; It is expressed by the participating teachers as authoritarian and oppressive, excessively normative, discrimination, biased, inability to produce solutions, inquiring, using authority as a threat, taking decisions alone, not being a role model, not taking initiative, ignoring the effort and transferring the work to someone else. School administrator behaviors that reduce teachers' professional belonging under the theme of negative communication; commanding, giving advice, accusing, constantly criticizing, scolding, judgmental, "I" language and shouting by the participant teachers. Under the theme of behaviors originating from negative personality traits, school administrator behaviors that reduce teachers' professional belonging; distrust, insensitivity, extreme skepticism, self-esteem, inconsistency, avoidance of responsibility, self-righteousness, interest-oriented and not open to criticism. Some of the opinions of the participating teachers on the subject are given below:

School administrators try to run schools like their own home. They are trying to get things done by giving orders to the teachers in an imperious way. Our opinions are not asked. When this happens, there is no desire to work, and we want to leave that school if we get the opportunity. (T 3).

Sometimes, optional tasks are forced by the manager as if they were compulsory. Teachers do not oppose to avoid conflict, but everyone does it blindly. Nobody wants to make an effort. (T 9).

The school principal's disregard for teachers' ideas and opinions causes teachers to feel worthless. A teacher who feels worthless may think that he is left alone in his school, and cannot be productive because his morale and motivation are low. He may want the lesson to end as soon as possible.(T13).

While managing the school, I worked with the school principal, who constantly reminded him of the laws and regulations and avoided taking the initiative. No one was happy at school, everyone had a state of uneasiness and fear. Even though they knew that they would not be appointed during the appointment period, almost all the teachers applied. (T16).

The fact that the school principal makes the teachers feel his authority as a punishment tool, both in meetings and in one-on-one conversations, and always blames the teachers in negative situations and sees them responsible, causes anger and weariness in the teachers. As such, teachers cannot take ownership of their jobs and inefficiency increases. (T20)

I was exposed to many injustices in arranging the curriculum, determining the days of the shift, and the distribution of students. My psyche is broken. I wanted to leave this school as soon as possible. I felt worthless because our school principal never asked us and did not take our opinions when making these adjustments. There were times when I could not devote myself to my work. (T 23).

Most of the time, the work we do at school is not seen by the administrators. There are always times when we are criticized. We do not see appreciation and thanks. This situation breaks our determination to work. We come to school with our feet back. (T 11).

4. Discussion

In this study, the behavior of school administrators was examined in the context of teachers' professional belonging. In the context of the first category of the research, the views of the participating teachers about the behaviors of school administrators that increase the professional belonging of teachers were examined. Teachers' views were gathered under four themes: managerial behaviors, effective communication, behaviors based on personality traits, and behaviors towards meeting social needs.

Under the theme of managerial behavior, participant teachers show that school administrators behave fairly and impartially, value and care about employees, include teachers in decisions, appreciate them, stand by the employee, trust the teacher, improve physical conditions, reduce bureaucracy, make things easier, empower the teacher, share authority, and accountability. They stated that being transparent, solving problems, behaving consistently, being democratic, open to cooperation, being conciliatory, taking initiative, being an example, being informative and guiding increase their professional belonging.

One of the main findings of the study is that the fair and impartial behavior of school administrators increases teachers' professional belonging. According to Van Knippenberg, et al. (2007), managers are accepted as the source of fair and unfair practices in the organization. According to İnce & Gül (2005), organizational justice; It is about whether the distribution of duties, wages and rewards, decision-making and informing processes, and social relations within the organization are perceived as fair by the employees. Çelik, (1999), on the other hand, draws attention to the fact that the school administrator should be impartial and fair in order to have a strong influence on teachers. Similarly, Eisenberger et al., (2002) managers who have a positive impact on employees are those who maintain a fair balance among employees. Perceptions about who/why the rewards and punishments are given at school, the distribution of lessons and extracurricular workload, the sharing of responsibilities, how the practices are carried out and how all these processes work are among the situations that determine the level of organizational justice in the school (Kalman & Gedikoğlu, 2014). According to Hoy and Tarter (2004), the level of organizational justice in the school also focuses on the behavior of the school administrator.

Participating teachers under the theme of administrative behaviors emphasizes that school administrators value and care about them. Beldağ & Yaylacı (2015) underline that school administrators who value their employees should give importance to the opinions and thoughts of teachers. Çelik (2010) states that the most important behavior types that increase the motivation of the employees are that the managers value and care about the opinions of the people they work with.

Within the scope of the current study, teachers stated that improving the physical conditions of school administrators increases their professional belonging. According to Fullan (2001), the principal is the person who helps teachers in reaching services in terms of equipment, physical and technical issues. It is known that teachers who have the necessary course materials and materials they need in their classrooms and who can use departments such as laboratories, libraries and gymnasiums at school will be more professionally willing. The role of school administrators is important in the preparation of the appropriate physical infrastructure necessary

for effective education in the school. According to Gürbüz, et al. (2013), it is important for school principals to provide appropriate physical conditions for their success.

In the study, teachers stated that school administrators' self-confidence increases their professional belonging. A trusted teacher will make an effort to do her best in a subject related to her profession. The phenomenon of trust has an important place in educational organizations. In this respect, it is of great importance that the relations between the stakeholders in schools are based on mutual trust. Studies have shown that trust functions as a motivator in coping with difficulties at school and is a key element in the development of productive group relationships (Hoy, Tarter & Witkoskie, 1992).

According to the research findings, the school administrators' behavior towards facilitating the work is another factor that is effective in the professional belonging of the teachers. Studies conducted in the literature on the roles expected to be performed by modern school principals define the most basic roles of principals as facilitators (Foley, 2001; O'Hair & Reitzug, 1997; Hall, 2005). Dönmez (2000) states that the roles of facilitating, teaching, expert consultancy, coordinating resources, communicative and supportive are the roles required by effective school leadership in the 21st century. According to Töremen, & Karakuş (2008), school administrators; They have to help the functioning of the school on the basis of human relations and within the framework of its unique characteristics, to produce high morale and to facilitate the work by eliminating the difficulties in this regard. Morrison (2007), on the other hand, emphasizes the importance of the school principal's displaying behaviors that make things easier at school.

In the study, teachers drew attention to the behaviors of school administrators to share authority. In the study conducted by Gürbüz, Erdem & Yıldırım (2013), the participants; They stated that the school principal should create an environment in which his employees will participate and contribute voluntarily for the success of the school, and that he should share these powers with his employees instead of using all his powers completely legally.

Another finding expressed by the teachers under the theme of administrative behaviors is that the school administrator's accountable and transparent behaviors increase teachers' belonging to their profession. Although accountability is about everyone involved in the education system, it basically focuses on the behavior of school administrators (Cooley and Shen 2003). Another structure that helps build trust in organizations is transparency, which is a part of accountability (Norman, Avolio & Luthans 2010). Providing timely and accurate information to stakeholders on issues concerning the organization also lays the groundwork for the establishment of an environment of trust in the organization (Kalman & Gedikoğlu, 2014). According to Eren (2001), organizational managers should be open in their decisions.

In the study, the teachers stated that the behaviors of the administrators that produce solutions to their problems affect their professional belonging positively. Çelikten (2004), in his research in primary schools, concluded that one of the characteristics that school principals should have is problem solver. According to Morrison (2007), the school principal should take an active role in solving the problems faced by the staff at school and be able to produce solutions to the problem.

Another important behavior of school administrators that increases teachers' professional belonging is being open to cooperation. Bakioğlu (2013) emphasizes in his study that school administrators should provide opportunities and opportunities to improve the cooperation of teachers. In another study on this subject, it is emphasized that administrators should encourage teachers to cooperate by supporting them (Gökçe, 2000).

Participating teachers drew attention to the importance of school principals' behavior towards taking initiative. The concept of initiative is a concept that focuses on increasing the effectiveness of their own individual performance and organizations by taking responsibilities beyond the role requirements, with the goals they create themselves. In this sense, initiative in school management can be considered as the extra contributions of school administrators that are compatible with the Basic Objectives of National Education, but not among the defined role requirements (Akın, 2012). Sevil & Bülbül (2019) state that school administrators should be

individuals with high self-esteem and take personal initiative in the creation of effective schools. However, there are studies that concluded that taking the initiative causes an increase in the desire to be involved in the work (Crant, 2000) and an increase in the level of emotional commitment to work (Hartog & Belschak, 2007).

Under the theme of effective communication, the participating teachers stated that school administrators' active listening, persuasion, providing feedback, inclusive speech, using humor, and engaging in moralizing behaviors increase their professional belonging. According to Gürbüz, Erdem, & Yıldırım (2013), effective communication has an important role in the success of school principals. In another study, it was concluded that effective principals have a role in establishing an effective communication in the school environment (Hallinger & Murphy (1986).

In the study, teachers expressed the importance of school administrators' active listening. Listening is an important part of successful interpersonal communication and relationships (Bodie, 2011). Listening skill is one of the important skills of organizational communication and leadership (Southart & Wolvin, 2009) Researches show that there are positive relationships between managers' attitudes towards listening and employees' attitudes towards the organization (Ellis, 2003; Young, 2009).

Teachers drew attention to the persuasive behavior of school administrators. According to Dawis (1984), if a successful manager can effectively persuade his employees to achieve common goals, it can be said to affect employees. Durukan (2006) states that good school administrators identify the potential of the personnel and convince them that they can do much better work than they do.

Another important finding under the theme of effective communication is that school administrators can use humor. Gürbüz, Erdem & Yıldırım, (2013) concluded that the skills of using humor are effective in the success of school principals, and Receptoğlu, (2008) concluded that teachers in the school of administrators who use humor in the workplace have higher job satisfaction.

Under the theme of behaviors originating from personality traits, participant teachers believe that school administrators should be honest and reliable, show self-respect, empathize, be sincere, be tolerant and optimistic, show understanding, be kind and gentle, show respect for different thoughts and opinions, control their anger, and respond to criticism. They stated that being open increases their professional belonging. The data of studies conducted in the fields of personality and organizational behavior reveal that personality is the most important factor directing the behavior of the individual, and in this context, it is related to both organizational performance (Barrick, Day & Lord, 1991) and the attitudes of employees. Organizational managers with different personality traits create different effects on employees (Atwater & Yammarino, 1993).

One of the main findings of the study is that the honest and reliable school administrators increase the professional belonging of the teachers. Reliability is knowing that the other person will support them whenever they need it. This sense of commitment is formed over time as a result of past experiences and becomes predictions for the future (Yılmaz, 2015). According to Taşçı & Eroğlu (2013), a manager is someone that all other personnel in the organization trust and respect. Eren (2001) states that managers should be honest.

Participating teachers draw attention to the importance of school administrators being tolerant and optimistic. Karaköse (2008) states in his study that the school principal should be tolerant and friendly towards the employees. In the study, the importance of school administrators' understanding of teachers was expressed. The most important factor that leads the institutions to success is that the superior-subordinate relations are based on understanding. (Kocabaş, & Karaköse, 2005).

Finally, in the research, managerial behaviors that increase teachers' professional belonging were expressed under the theme of meeting social needs. School administrator behaviors under this theme; It was expressed by the participating teachers as organizing social activities, meeting the need for rest and providing togetherness. Akıncı (2002) states that managers also have social aspects of employees, and they should consider different

socio-psychological expectations and needs besides their economic expectations. Supportive managers are people who take into account the needs of their employees (Eisenberger et al., 2002).

In the study, the behaviors of school administrators, which reduce the professional belonging of teachers, were also determined. The opinions of the teachers were gathered under three themes: managerial behaviors, negative communication and behaviors originating from personality traits.

Participating teachers under the theme of managerial behaviors; School administrators' being authoritarian and oppressive, excessively normative, discriminatory, biased, incapable of producing solutions, questioning, using authority as a threat, taking decisions alone, not being a role model, not taking initiative, ignoring the effort and transferring the work to someone else, reveal their professional belongings. has been reported to decrease. It is known that the influence of the management styles of the managers is important in directing the attitudes and behaviors of the employees, and in the high morale and productivity. Because the manager has the power to determine what the employees should do (Koçel, 2014).

One of the main findings of the study, which reduces the professional belonging of teachers, is that school administrators behave authoritatively and oppressively. While authoritarian managers are oppressive and threatening to their subordinates, they are also extremely obedient and flattering towards their superiors. They expect similar behaviors from their subordinates (Özgür, 2011). Authoritarian rulers use rewards, punishments, and laws as sources of power. This type of leader is task oriented. However, productivity is low because the organizational climate is not suitable (Razi, 2003). Those who work in an authoritarian and oppressive management style are often unhappy, and this is reflected in their motivation, performance and productivity. These teachers are also highly likely to have negative feelings and attitudes towards their administrators and schools. Teachers do not feel that they belong to their school, they will do the tasks that need to be done because they have to do it, and when they find the opportunity, they will go on the path of changing institutions. A teacher who does not feel that he belongs to his school will not have a low commitment to the school and will not own his school, and will not show the necessary positive behaviors if he represents his school outside (Argon, & Dilekçi, 2014).

In the study, the teachers drew attention to the excessive prescriptive behavior of the administrators. According to Frese, et al. (1996), bureaucracy and excessive adherence to rules cause the school administrator to be insufficient in meeting the expectations and needs of today's schools and make him passive, only obliged to fulfill what is said.

Another important finding that reduces the professional belonging of teachers under the theme of administrative behaviors is the discrimination behaviors of school administrators. It is the exposure of the employee to different treatments in matters unrelated to his job (Özkan & Özkan, 2010). Wood, Breakey & Niven, (2013) concluded in their research that some negative organizational outcomes such as stress, dissatisfaction and low motivation occur in employees who are exposed to workplace discrimination. Demirel (2011) states that the deepening of discrimination among employees will negatively affect intra-organizational communication.

Another remarkable finding that emerged in the research is that the use of the powers of the administrators as a threat against the employees reduces the professional belonging of the teachers. According to Hale & Moorman (2003), "order-command" type of administrative practices no longer make sense in existing school systems; it succeeds. Gurbuz et al. (2013) states that it is important for school principals to use their authorities correctly in order to be successful.

Participating teachers stated that ignoring their efforts by school administrators reduced their professional belonging. In other studies on the subject, it has been concluded that school administrators' ignoring and not appreciating the work of teachers causes a loss of motivation in teachers (Büyükses, 2010; Demir, 2007). Ada et al., (2014) express the importance of administrators seeing and approving teachers' positive work.

School administrator behaviors that reduce teachers' professional belonging under the theme of negative communication; commanding, giving advice, accusing, constantly criticizing, scolding, judgmental, "I" language and shouting by the participant teachers. The lack of healthy mutual interaction and communication can lead to disconnection and conflicts between the administration and the teachers. In this respect, it can be said that interpersonal relations and communication play an important role in educational organizations (Bursalıoğlu, 2003). According to Ada, et al. (2015), school administrators must have effective communication skills in order to create a positive atmosphere in the institutions they manage.

Finally, in the study, under the theme of behaviors originating from negative personality traits, school administrator behaviors that reduce teachers' professional belonging; distrust, insensitivity, extreme skepticism, self-esteem, inconsistency, avoidance of responsibility, self-righteousness, interest-oriented and not open to criticism. Koçel (2014) states that with the concentration of all powers in the manager, overconfidence, self-admiration, not listening to and distrusting others, making quick decisions without analysis and with exaggerated self-confidence, can turn into a personality structure that is surrounded by enemies and wants everything to flow under its own control. is doing. The types of behavior that individuals with different personality traits in managerial positions show towards their employees will also be different. As a result of not matching individuals with these different personality traits with appropriate management levels, the health of the organization will deteriorate and employees will be adversely affected (Korkmaz, 2006).

5. Conclusion

When the research findings are evaluated in general; It is seen that the behaviors of school administrators have an important place in the professional belonging of teachers. The fact that the teaching profession is a profession that requires great dedication reveals the importance of the concept of professional belonging, which is one of the most important factors affecting the organizational behavior of the individual. For this reason, in the research, the behavior of school administrators in the professional belonging of teachers was tried to be examined in depth. As a result; It is seen that the behaviors of school administrators are one of the determining factors in the professional belonging of teachers. It is thought that the effectiveness of teachers with high professional belonging will also be high. Therefore, it is considered that the effective execution of the teaching profession will create an effective education-teaching process at school, and thus contribute to the achievement of student learning at the desired level.

5.1. Suggestions

In this study, the participants emphasized the behaviors of school administrators in the professional belonging of teachers. Based on the results of the research, it should be ensured that school administrators are aware of the importance of the behaviors of teachers in their professional belonging, and awareness trainings should be organized for this. In the research, the participants drew attention to the managerial behaviors exhibited by the school administrators in the professional belonging of the teachers. For this reason, it may be necessary to receive applied and theoretical training at the graduate level, which includes administrative behaviors, in appointment to school administrators. Another finding revealed the importance of school administrators' effective communication with teachers. Therefore, the communication skills that school administrators should have should be determined and given to the administrator candidates before the task of administration. Another remarkable finding obtained from the research is that the behaviors of school administrators based on their personality traits are effective on teachers' professional belonging. Regarding this situation, the personality factor should be taken into consideration before the manager appointments made by the Ministry of National Education. In the study, the participants talked about the importance of meeting social needs in the professional belonging of teachers. Accordingly, joint activities should be organized in which administrators and teachers will get to know each other better, and the social needs of teachers should be taken into account in these activities. Finally, based on this research, it is suggested that researchers investigate other factors that affect teachers' professional belonging.

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